

Synthesis of Potential Amoebicides. Part XXIII

A. B. Sen and S. B. Singh

Ethers and esters containing dichloroacetamide grouping have been synthesised as potential amoebicides.

The dichloroacetamide grouping, when introduced as a pharmacophore moiety to a variety of carrier systems, has been known to yield potent antiamoebic compounds, such as entamide¹, chlorophenoxamide², and others³⁻⁴. The compounds are characterised by their high chemotherapeutic index and little or no side effects.

Benzoylation and benzylation of the free hydroxyl group of entamide ($\alpha\alpha$ -dichloro-*N*-methyl-*p*-hydroxyacetanilide) have been found to markedly enhance its antiamoebic activity, but the effect of substitution of halogen and other groups in the phenyl nucleus of the benzyl or benzoyl group has not been studied, although these substitutions are known to cause a marked increase in activity in other cases⁵.

The synthesis of a number of substituted benzoyl, benzyl, and sulphonyl derivatives of $\alpha\alpha$ -dichloro-*N*-methyl-*p*-substituted acetanilides (I) has therefore been undertaken.

Further, the ether linkage of chlorophenoxamide, a well-known antiamoebic drug, has been replaced by a benzoyloxy grouping in order to study the effect of this change on the antiamoebic activity. The reactions involved in the synthesis are shown below.

1. Brtsov *et al.*, *Trans. Roy. Soc., Trop. Med. Hyg.*, 1956, **50**, 182; Woodruff, *Brit. Med. J.*, 1956, **1**, 282.
2. Deasneri *et al.*, "*Chem. & Antibiot.*," 1960, **10**, 626.
3. Surrey *et al.*, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, **76**, 2214; 1955, **77**, 3798, 5406; 1956, **78**, 2573, 3834.
4. Logemann *et al.*, *Il Farmaco*, 1958, **13**, 139.
5. Kidd and Wright, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1962, 1420.

EXPERIMENTAL

Benzoyl Derivative of $\alpha\alpha$ -Dichloro-N-methyl-p-substituted Acetanilides.—Substituted benzoyl chloride (0.01M) was added during 15 min. to a stirred solution of $\alpha\alpha$ -dichloro-N-methyl-p-hydroxyacetanilide (0.01M) in dry pyridine (20 ml). After 24 hr., the pyridine was removed under reduced pressure and the residue diluted with water when a solid was obtained. It was recrystallised from dilute ethanol. The m. p., yields, and analyses of these compounds are recorded in Table I.

TABLE I

R.	M.P.	% Yield.	Formula.	% Nitrogen.	
				Found.	Reqd.
<i>p</i> -Cl	75°	45	C ₁₆ H ₁₂ O ₃ NCl ₃	3.40	3.76
<i>m</i> -Cl	115°	65	C ₁₆ H ₁₂ O ₃ NCl ₃	3.51	3.76
<i>o</i> -Cl	156°	40	C ₁₆ H ₁₂ O ₃ NCl ₃	3.48	3.76
<i>p</i> -NO ₂	127°	40	C ₁₆ H ₁₂ O ₃ N ₂ Cl ₂	7.10	7.31
6-Cl-3-NO ₂	135°	50	C ₁₆ H ₁₁ O ₃ N ₂ Cl ₃	6.40	6.71
3,5-Di-NO ₂	160°	25	C ₁₆ H ₁₁ O ₇ N ₃ Cl ₂	9.45	9.81

Benzyl Derivatives of $\alpha\alpha$ -Dichloro-N-methyl-p-substituted Acetanilides.—The substituted benzyl chloride (0.01M), $\alpha\alpha$ -dichloro-N-methyl-p-hydroxyacetanilide (0.01M), and calcined potassium carbonate (0.012M) were refluxed in acetone (50 ml) for 24 hr. The compounds were isolated in the usual way.

The benzenesulphonyl derivatives of entamide were obtained from the potassium salt of entamide in the usual way³. The m. p., yields, and analyses of the benzyl and benzenesulphonyl derivatives of $\alpha\alpha$ -dichloro-N-methyl-p-substituted acetanilides are recorded in Table II.

TABLE II

R	X.	M.P.	% Yield.	Formula.	% Nitrogen.	
					Found.	Reqd.
<i>p</i> -NO ₂	CH ₂	114°	70	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ O ₄ N ₂ Cl ₂	7.32	7.59
<i>p</i> -Cl	CH ₂	105°	80	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ O ₂ NCl ₃	3.70	3.90
H	CH ₂	72°	80	C ₁₆ H ₁₅ O ₂ NCl ₂	4.10	4.32
H	SO ₂	152°	65	C ₁₅ H ₁₃ O ₄ NCl ₂ S	3.62	3.74
<i>p</i> -Me	SO ₂	140°	65	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ O ₄ NCl ₂ S	3.42	3.61

Schiff's Bases of m- and o-Hydroxybenzaldehydes with Ethanolamine.—The aromatic aldehyde (0.1M) and ethanolamine (0.1M) in anhydrous ethanol (50 ml) were refluxed on a water bath for 2 hr. The Schiff bases were isolated in the usual way and purified either

by recrystallisation or by distillation under reduced pressure. The m.p. or b. p., yields, and analyses are recorded in Table IIIA.

p & *o*-(Hydroxy)-*N*-benzylethanolamines.—The Schiff bases (0.1*M*) were dissolved in hot anhydrous ethanol (200 ml) and then reduced catalytically with Pd-C at a pressure of 60 lb./sq. in. After filtering the catalyst and removing the solvent, an oily liquid was obtained which was purified by distillation under reduced pressure. The b. p., yields, and analyses of the amines are recorded in Table III B.

TABLE III A

Aromatic aldehyde.	M.P. or B. P.	%Yield.	Formula.	% Nitrogen.	
				Found.	Reqd.
<i>p</i> -OH	175°	96%	C ₉ H ₁₁ O ₂ N	8.20	8.48
<i>o</i> -OH	140°/8mm	80	C ₉ H ₁₁ O ₂ N	8.16	8.48

TABLE IIIB

Ethanolamine.	B.P.	%Yield.	Formula.	% Nitrogen.	
				Found.	Reqd.
<i>p</i> -Hydroxybenzyl-	155°/5mm	75	C ₉ H ₁₃ O ₂ N	8.26	8.38
<i>o</i> ,,	160°/6	70	C ₉ H ₁₃ O ₂ N	8.40	8.38

p & *o*-Hydroxybenzyl-*N*-(2-hydroxyethyl) dichloroacetamide.—The amine (10.02 g.) was dissolved in a mixture of *N*-NaOH solution (50 ml) and ethylene dichloride (40 ml); the mixture was cooled to 0° under stirring. Dichloroacetyl chloride (9.0 g.), dissolved in ethylene dichloride (30 ml), was then added dropwise and the mixture was allowed to attain the room temperature. The ethylene dichloride layer was separated, successively washed with *N*-NaOH solution, water, *N*-HCl, and water. It was then dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate and the solvent removed by distillation. The residual liquid was purified by distillation under reduced pressure. The b.p., yields, and analyses are recorded in Table IV.

TABLE IV

Benzyl- <i>N</i> -(hydroxyethyl) dichloroacetamide.	B.P.	%Yield.	Formula.	% Nitrogen.	
				Found.	Reqd.
<i>p</i> -OH	135°/5mm	70	C ₁₁ H ₁₃ O ₃ NCl ₂	4.84	5.04
<i>o</i> -OH	142°/7	65	C ₁₁ H ₁₃ O ₃ NCl ₂	4.94	5.04

The benzoyl derivatives of *p*- (and *o*)-hydroxybenzyl -*N* (2-hydroxyethyl)dichloroacetamides were obtained in the usual way⁵. The m.p., yields, and analyses are reported in Table V.

TABLE V

Benzoyl chloride.	Hydroxybenzyl -N-(2-hydroxyethyl) dichloroacetamide.	M.P.	%Yield.	Formula.	%Nitrogen.	
					Found.	Reqd.
1. <i>p</i> -Cl	<i>p</i> -Cl	210°	40	C ₁₈ H ₁₆ O ₄ NCl ₂	3.56	3.38
2. <i>p</i> -NO ₂	..	228°	42	C ₁₈ H ₁₆ O ₆ N ₂ Cl ₂	6.26	6.56
3. <i>p</i> -NO ₂	<i>o</i> -	105°	30	C ₁₈ H ₁₆ O ₆ N ₂ Cl ₂	6.26	6.56

DEPARTMENT OF CHEMISTRY,
LUCKNOW UNIVERSITY,
LUCKNOW.

Received March 30, 1965.